

Characterisation of two infrared heaters

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We derive the emissive properties as functions of the supplied power for two infrared heaters, one featuring a carbon fibre filament, the other based on ceramic elements heated by electric resistance. In particular, we define the law between the input voltage and wavelength at peak emissive power.

1 Infrared lamp with carbon fibre filament

We derive the peak wavelength of the infrared emission from the Turbo Neighborhood TN35E heater as a function of both voltage and power. The heater features a carbon fibre filament enclosed in a glass bulb filled with inert gas.

1.1 Surface of the filament

The carbon fibre filament of the Turbo TN35E infrared lamp can be modelled as a ribbon with a width $w = 0.27 \text{ cm}$ whose geometric axis is a helix with a pitch $p = 0.4 \text{ cm}$ and a diameter $D = 1 \text{ cm}$ (Figure 1). The filament forms a total of $N = 25$ coils over a length of 40 cm .

It can be shown that the length of the geometric axis of a coil of a helix with diameter D and pitch p is given by

$$l = \sqrt{\pi^2 D^2 + p^2}. \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the surface of a single coil of filament is approximately given by

$$s = d \cdot l = w \sqrt{\pi^2 D^2 + p^2}, \quad (2)$$

and the total surface of the filament is

$$S = N \cdot s = Nw \sqrt{\pi^2 D^2 + p^2}. \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: The carbon fibre filament of the infrared lamp can be modelled as a ribbon with a helicoidal geometric axis. The external diameter of the helix is D , the width of the ribbon is d , and p is the pitch.

1.2 Temperature of the filament

Let us denote the power supplied to the lamp as Π and let the fraction converted into radiative power be η . According to the Stefan-Boltzmann law, the energy radiated by a unit surface of the filament in a unit of time is given by

$$e = \epsilon\sigma T^4, \quad (4)$$

where T is the absolute temperature of the filament surface, $\sigma = 5.67051 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}^4)$ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, and ϵ is the total emissivity of the filament surface. Therefore, the total power radiated by the filament is given by

$$\eta\Pi = eS = \epsilon\sigma T^4 Nw\sqrt{\pi^2 D^2 + p^2}, \quad (5)$$

where we have considered equations 3 and 4. We can therefore derive the temperature of the filament as a function of the power supplied to the lamp:

$$T = \sqrt[4]{\frac{\eta\Pi}{\epsilon\sigma Nw\sqrt{\pi^2 D^2 + p^2}}}. \quad (6)$$

We assume $\eta = 0.95$ (as indicated by the manufacturer) and $\epsilon = 0.95$, according to [1], appendix D. This function is plotted in Figure 2. This is a simplified model, because part of the emissive power is reabsorbed by the filament itself, either because of direct incidence or because the filament is hit by a fraction of the power reflected by the aluminium reflector. In other words, the temperature in equation 6 must be seen as a lower limit of the actual temperature of the filament.

We can calculate the hemispheric emissive power of the filament by applying Planck's law and assuming the filament as an opaque body with an emissivity of 0.95:

Figure 2: Temperature of the carbon fibre filament, as a function of the power absorbed by the lamp (equation 6)

$$e(\lambda, T) = \epsilon \frac{2\pi C_1}{\lambda^5 (e^{\frac{C_2}{\lambda T}} - 1)}, \quad (7)$$

where $C_1 = 0.59552197 \times 10^{-16} W \cdot m^2 / sr$ and $C_2 = 0.01438769 mK$. A plot of $e(\lambda, T)$ for several values of the absolute temperature of the filament is reported in Figure 3.

1.3 Radiative properties as functions of the voltage

In our experimental setting, the voltage can be modulated via a dimmer by SiRyder. Therefore, we are interested in expressing the filament temperature and the radiative properties of the filament as a function of the voltage. To do so, we collected 15 measures of voltage and power using a Shelly Plug S, a Wi-Fi plug that provides real-time metrics via a dedicated App. We then regressed the voltage against the power (Figure 4). We find the empirical law:

$$Voltage = 0.24 \times Power + 56.47 \text{ Volts}. \quad (8)$$

By substituting equation 8 into equation 6 we find the filament temperature as a function of the input voltage (Figure 5). We can also calculate the wavelength at peak emissive power by substituting the experimental law $T = T(voltage)$ into the Wien displacement law $\lambda_{max} = \frac{C_3}{T}$, where $C_3 = 0.0029 mK$ (Figure 6).

Figure 3: hemispheric emissive power of the carbon fibre filament, for different absolute temperatures, according to equation 9

2 Infrared lamp with ceramic elements

In what follows, we study the radiative properties of a ceramic infrared element, manufactured by Under Control Instruments LTD. This component features a K type thermocouple coated to the ceramic. Therefore, in this case we won't need to derive the surface temperature from the supplied power, as we did in the previous example. We need to find a way to estimate the efficiency, though.

2.1 Geometry of the ceramic element

The surface of the ceramic element is a cylindrical segment with radius of curvature $R = 6.025 \text{ cm}$, length $L = 12 \text{ cm}$, and width $W = 6 \text{ cm}$. As can be seen in (Figure 7), one of the two faces of the element faces a reflector, therefore, the surface that is involved in active radiation is

$$S = 2\theta RL = 75.19 \text{ cm}^2, \quad (9)$$

where $\theta = 30^\circ$.

Figure 4: Linear regression between power and voltage input to the infrared lamp, for 15 values of voltage. The electric potential was modulated via a SiRyder dimmer and data were collected by a Wi-Fi plug (Shelly Plug S). The p value for this regression is 2.7×10^{-8} .

2.2 Efficiency as a function of voltage

We collected power and ceramic element temperature for several values of the input voltage. We used a K type thermocouple coated on the radiative element to measure temperature, and a Shelly Plug S to collect voltage and power (Table 1). In agreement with equation 10, the efficiency of the element can be written:

$$\eta = \frac{eS}{\Pi} = \frac{\epsilon\sigma T^4 S}{\Pi}, \quad (10)$$

where $\epsilon = 0.9$ is the total emissivity of ceramic ([1], appendix D) and Π is the power supplied to the lamp.

2.3 Radiative properties

Once we find the empirical law that gives voltage from power (via linear regression) using data from Table 1 (see Figure 8), it is possible to define the efficiency as a function of voltage, as in Figure 9). We require a law for the surface temperature as a function of power (Figure 10) to calculate the wavelength value at peak emissive power, given the voltage, as in Figure 11.

Figure 5: Filament temperature as a function of the input voltage.

References

- [1] Robert Siegel and John R. Howell. *Thermal Radiation Heat Transfer*. Hemisphere Publishing Corporation, Washington, DC, 3rd edition, 1992.

Figure 6: Wavelength at peak emissive power as a function of input voltage.

Figure 7: Ceramic element and aluminium reflector.

Figure 8: Linear regression between power and voltage, using data from Table 1.

Figure 9: Efficiency of the ceramic element coupled with a reflector as a function of voltage.

voltage(V)	temperature (°C)	power (W)
42	194.1	60.6
58	267.6	95.7
75	329	129.2
91	378.7	169.1
107	422.4	202
114	442.5	218.3
133	495.4	265.1
151	543	312.1
174	588	359.4
198	640.7	399.3
220	680.7	465.1

Table 1: Experimental measures of voltage, temperature, and power for the ceramic element.

Figure 10: Polynomial regression of the second order between voltage and temperature, using data from Table 1.

Figure 11: Wavelength at peak emissive power for the ceramic element coupled with a reflector, according to Wien displacement law.